

EMSEA CONFERENCE INFORMATION BOOKLET

ANNUAL CONFERENCE Ostend, Belgium

17-19 SEPTEMBER 2025

WELCOME

Dear participants,

EMSEA is delighted to welcome you to the vibrant coastal city of Ostend.

Every year, the EMSEA Annual Conference brings together educators, scientists, policymakers, and advocates from across Europe and beyond. We invite you to share ideas, forge collaborations, and celebrate our collective efforts toward an ocean literate society.

We thank our hosts, partners, and sponsors who made this gathering possible, and most of all—you for being part of our community.

Enjoy the conference, and enjoy Ostend!

Warm regards,

The EMSEA Organising Committee

This document sets out some of the important conference information for you to get prepared.

Innovative Ocean Literacy for a Sustainable Blue Economy

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The transition to a sustainable blue economy requires more than technological advancements and policy alignment – it requires a **profound understanding from stakeholders of their role in the transition**. The (the Partnership) recognises **Ocean Literacy (OL) as a cross-cutting enabler** supporting this transition, equipping stakeholders with the knowledge and tools necessary to make informed decisions. To foster this transformation, the Partnership has developed **diverse and innovative methodologies** to embed OL into its co-funded projects to ensure research findings resonate beyond the scientific community, and to showcase the importance of a ‘blue economy’ literacy to relevant stakeholders.

This presentation will highlight the Partnership’s multi-faceted approach to OL, demonstrating how tailored formats and methodologies enhance awareness, foster collaboration, and drive sustainable innovation within blue economy sectors. Key initiatives include:

- **Podcasts and Blue Economy web capsules:** designed to make complex scientific and policy topics accessible, these media formats translate - research and policy insights into engaging and digestible content for a broad audience around blue economy key words (aquaculture, coastal resilience, etc.).
- **OL training for co-funded projects:** to maximise their impact, the Partnership provides dedicated training sessions for its co-funded projects, equipping them with the skills to integrate OL principles into their work and communicate findings effectively to relevant stakeholders.
- **World Café sessions in regional blue economy workshops:** these interactive sessions bring together researchers, industry representatives, policymakers, and local communities to facilitate open dialogue and knowledge co-creation, ensuring that OL is embedded within regional and sector-specific blue economy initiatives.
- **Integration of OL in future Partnership funding calls:** acknowledging that research projects play a crucial role in advancing OL, the Partnership actively encourages applicants to incorporate OL activities in their proposals. By doing so, projects can enhance their societal impact, engage stakeholders more effectively, and contribute to wider knowledge-sharing efforts.
- **Ocean Literacy Toolkit:** the Partnership has developed a comprehensive toolkit compiling external publications, learning tools, and its own resources on OL. Designed to inform and empower stakeholders, this publication serves as a go-to guide for integrating OL into blue economy strategies and initiatives.

- **Ocean Literacy for Businesses:** the Partnership has worked to understand the perspectives of ocean industries on sustainability practices, resulting in a deliverable that outlines key challenges and recommendations. To further disseminate and implement these findings, the Partnership is organising a dedicated workshop on OL for businesses, in collaboration with EU4Ocean and EMSEA, fostering engagement between industry, academia, and policymakers.

Through these initiatives, the Partnership is fostering a culture of informed decision-making in the blue economy, where researchers, industries, and policymakers are empowered to align economic activities with ocean sustainability. This presentation will not only highlight the Partnership's OL strategy but also explore how innovative communication, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement approaches can accelerate the transition towards a truly sustainable blue economy.

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